

ENCOURAGING QUALITY ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED INFORMATION SYSTEMS: A HANDS-ON APPROACH

Extended Abstract

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become an essential and indispensable part of the modern information system in recent years. AI-based systems are software systems where traditional software components are combined with AI components (Felderer and Ramler, 2021). Although AI has been a part of software engineering for many years, its recent ubiquity directs us to the field's maturation. Among others, an important topic is software quality assurance. The involvement of AI in software systems has led to numerous new challenges. Felderer and Ramler (2021) depicts some of them. E.g., non-deterministic behaviour in terms of vaguely- or non-defined expected outcomes, accuracy, and correctness measures and others. To address those challenges, new and adapted approaches for assuring the quality of AI-based software systems must be developed, tested, and implemented.

The awareness of changes in software quality assurance processes due to the involvement of AI-components have to be adequately presented and introduced early in software engineering education. Enriching the traditional software quality assurance topics, such as testing and software metrics, with challenges and solutions, connected to AI is essential. In order to maximize the efficiency of the learning process, a variety of innovative teaching approaches could be used. The Learning pyramid states that knowledge acquisition is higher if the students are actively involved in teaching approaches (Letrud and Hernes, 2016). Therefore, we designed a focused workshop session covering AI-based system software testing. We implemented the workshop at the university and master's degree study programs in Informatics and Data Technologies within Quality Assurance study courses. The workshop's main objective was to introduce the students to challenges connected to testing AI-based information systems, where they could gather knowledge through first-hand experiences.

The is presented in Figure 1. We prepared three different software applications that include an AI component, which were a target application for testing. They were selected so, that they include a different type of AI-based components:

- The first application was from insurance domain, i.e., fraud detection software (*Fraudster*),
- the aim of the second application provided the name of the town while driving with the help of local traffic signs (*Locator*) and
- the third application generated different topics poems in various languages (*Poet*).

The *Fraudster* is an application of traditional machine-learning model with supervised learning. We made sure, that the model has built-in several cases that generate obvious errors. For example: when a client insures a car against accidents that result in broken glasses, and the next day issues a claim on exactly this accident, which is a case of highly probable fraud, our model reports a fraud probability of 0%. The *Locator* application is typical OCR / image recognition application. We made sure it works excellent on traffic signs, but made sure that it has some problems, such as distinguishing between road signs and other informative banners. The *Poet* application is a typical application of LLM, which enable users to request a poem on specific topic (love, nature, childhood etc.) using a selected language (English, Hungarian, Slovenian, French etc.). The generated poem should be 2 stanzas of 4 lines each. We made sure, that the application boasts of defects. E.g., sometimes it would generate only 1 stanza. Or it would, sometimes mix languages, generate 2 identical stanzas, or, in a marginal language create a text of different type (e.g., instructions for using the washing machine).

While we were curious, how will the students organize themselves in order to find as many errors as possible, we divided them into groups, and they entered the competition driven through *three* phases:

- Defining *software test strategy* and *plan*.
- Defining *test cases*.
- *Testing* implementation based on outputs from 1) and 2) and *error reporting*.

Figure 1. A bird-eye view on the workshop structure.

Each group had to prepare artefacts, such we regularly use in traditional testing (test plan, test strategy, test cases) and implement the testing for all three applications. After each phase, the instructors graded their work, providing them points considering several criteria. The assessment form is depicted in Figure 2. For example, in the second phase, we rated the test cases according to how systematically they were prepared, how innovative they are and how adequate they are to a particular case. Especially the innovation criterion offered an interesting insight into students’ understanding and coping with the challenges of AI-based systems appropriately.

	Phase 1: Defining software test strategy/plan			Phase 2: Defining test cases			Phase 3: Testing and error reporting		
	Systematicity	Innovation	Automatization level	Systematicity	Innovation	Adequacy	Systematicity	Automatization level	Found errors
Fraudster									
Locator									
Poet									

Figure 2. The assessment form used in the workshop.

At the end of the workshop, we gathered students' opinions with a short questionnaire on the implementation experience. The objective of the first part of the survey was to assess and gain knowledge, while the second part aimed at gathering their opinions regarding the implemented workshop. The survey participants were undergraduate and master's degree students. The most challenging task for the master's degree students was defining the test plan and strategy, followed by test implementation and error reporting. On the other hand, undergraduate students perceived the most challenging phase 3, namely test implementation and error reporting, followed by the definition of test cases. The most challenging task, regarding to the questionnaire results, was to properly test the *Fraudster* application, followed by the. We also asked the students about the perceived peculiarities when testing AI-based information systems. Most of their answers were connected to unspecified results and difficulties in achieving reproducibility. They also used the chatbots within the assignments, but according to their opinion, the results they gathered were just partially applicable and usable.

The gamified format of the workshop, with elements of points and leader boards, has further encouraged the students' engagement. According to the results gathered in the final survey, their attitude towards teaching, which includes practical hands-on approaches, is very positive. They rated the approach as interesting, with a mean value of 4.5 and 4, and suitable to their educational wishes and learning preferences, with a mean value of 4.4 and 3.8.

References

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